

Experimental investigation of a CPVT collector coupled with a wedge PVT receiver

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experimental investigation of a photovoltaic-thermal solar collector (commonly known as PVT) that generates both electricity and heat from the same gross area. PVT solar collectors, in theory, achieve higher combined electrical and heat yields. Additionally, PVT enables a thermal coupling between PV cells and a heat transfer cooling medium. Electrical and thermal outdoor testing measurements have been performed on a low concentration PVT solar collector based on a parabolic reflector geometry with a wedge PVT receiver. Several outdoor experiments have been carried out and presented, such as daily instantaneous electrical and thermal performance efficiency diagrams, as well as optical efficiency charts. Moreover, an electrical Incidence Angle Modifier (for both transversal and longitudinal directions) assessment has been performed and presented. Furthermore, an overall heat loss coefficient of $4.1 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot ^\circ\text{C}$ has been attained. A measured thermal optical and electrical efficiency of 59% and 8% have been achieved, respectively. Additionally, the placement of the wedge receiver shown to be very sensitive to high incidence angles, as the electrical transversal Incidence Angle Modifier factor decreases significantly after reaching its electrical peak efficiency at 10° .

1. Introduction

The electrical efficiency of PV cells typically corresponds to a fraction of the incident solar radiation with 22% for multi-crystalline and 27% for mono-crystalline silicon wafer-based technology (tested under laboratory conditions and presented by Fraunhofer, 2020), which leaves the remaining share to be converted into heat, which will increase the overall collector temperature and a consequent drop in electrical efficiency (Ali, 2020). Moreover, by combining both Thermal (T) and Photovoltaic (PV) technologies, higher total efficiencies can be achieved in a photovoltaic-thermal (PVT) solar collector. PVT collectors extract the excess thermal energy generated by the PV cells employing a Heat Transfer cooling Fluid (HTF), increasing electrical efficiencies due to lower PV cell temperatures. Consequently, Lämmle et al. (2020) allocated (in a schematic view, under the IEA-SHC Task 60: ‘Application of PVT collectors’) the different PVT technologies according to different parameters, such as HTF (typically water, since it increases the electrical and thermal efficiency (Abdullah et al., 2020), operating temperatures up to 120°C (Kalogirou, 2014), system design and layout (i.e. unglazed, glazed, and concentrating). Also, PVT technologies were categorized by its system application category (i.e. heat pump from -10°C to $+25^\circ\text{C}$,

swimming pools from $+20^\circ\text{C}$ to $+40^\circ\text{C}$, domestic hot water and space heating ($+20^\circ\text{C}$ to $+80^\circ\text{C}$), and process heat from $+40^\circ\text{C}$ up to $+120^\circ\text{C}$).

In recent years, several studies on PVT technologies have emerged, which ranged from simulation of PVT performance measurements to PVT technology reviews, as well as, energy and exergy analysis of PVT technologies. A review on the advantages and limitations of CPVT systems focused on HTF, design components and the latest applications, has been offered by George et al. (2019). Additionally, Herez et al. (2020) presented a review on PVT where different classifications, applications and new systems were introduced. Guarracino et al. (2019) focused on electrical and thermal performance characterization of flat PVT solar collectors, which concluded that by adding a glass cover, the thermal efficiency can be improved, but on the other hand, the electrical efficiency decreased due to the glass transmittance. Additionally, energy simulation models for PVT systems as the one presented by Aste et al. (2016) have been developed, which take into account all factors and parameters involved in the energy performance of an uncovered PVT collector.

Kumar et al. (2021) were able to model, simulate and experimentally evaluate the performance of a PVT collector, which reached thermal efficiencies of around 75%. Additionally, Tripathi and Tiwari (2019)

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Nomenclature

Symbol Description [Unit]

θ_c	Acceptance half-angle [°]
T_a	Ambient temperature [°C]
$A_{aperture}$	Aperture area [m ²]
G_b	Beam irradiance [W/m ²]
A_c	Collector area [m ²]
T_{in}	Collector inlet temperature [°C]
T_{col}	Collector mean temperature [(T _{out} -T _{in})/2, °C]
T_{out}	Collector outlet temperature [°C]
β	Collector tilt angle [°]
C_i	Concentration factor [-]
I_{mpp}	Current maximum power point [A]
G_d	Diffuse irradiance [W/m ²]
U_1	First-order heat loss coefficient [W/m ² .°C]
P_{mpp}	Maximum power point [W]
n	Normal to the surface [-]
V_{oc}	Open circuit voltage [V]
η_{opt}	Optical efficiency [%]
η_0	Peak collector efficiency at $\Delta T = 0$ K [-]
θ_p	Projection angle [°]
$A_{receiver}$	Receiver area [m ²]
$I_{sc, measured}$	Short circuit current (measured) [A]

$I_{sc, standard module}$	Short circuit current (standard module) [A]
γ_s	Solar azimuth angle [°]
θ_z	Solar zenith angle [°]
θ_{NS}	South projection angle [°]
G	Solar irradiance (global) [W/m ²]
ρ	Solar reflector reflectance [-]
τ	Solar glass transmittance [-]
P_{el}	Specific electrical power output [W/m ²]
c_p	Specific heat [J/K]
Q_{th}	Specific thermal power output [W/m ²]
$\eta_{opt,theo.}$	Theoretical optical efficiency [%]
V_{mpp}	Voltage maximum power point [V]

Abbreviations

CPC	Compound Parabolic Collectors
CPVT	Concentrating Photovoltaic-Thermal
c-Si	Crystalline silicon
HTF	Heat Transfer cooling Fluid
IAM	Incidence Angle Modifier
IV	Current-Voltage
LCPVT	Low Concentrating Photovoltaic-Thermal
PV	Photovoltaic
PVT	Photovoltaic-Thermal
T	Thermal

presented new energy matrices, life cycle costs and carbon mitigation methods for an open-loop CPVT collector. On the other hand, Tomar et al. (2017) developed an analytical model for temperature dependency, which showed improvements in both electrical, thermal and energy efficiencies.

Moreover, Jonas et al. (2019) presented a novel PVT performance model, which has been proposed as a standardized performance model for PVT collectors. Additionally, Nasseriyan et al. (2020) developed a PVT numerical model through a CFD software to predict the influence of the HTF temperature, thermal insulation and collector tilt angle in the overall performance of a CPVT solar collector.

Regarding experimental measurements, Maatallah et al. (2019) compared the experimental performance of a water-based PVT panel using phase change materials with standardized PV modules, which showed an improvement in the electrical performance of + 17 %_{rel} in comparison to a standard PV module. Kazem et al. (2020) studied several PVT systems with variable water flow channels and compared the electrical performance with a standard PV module. The proposed systems were successful in reducing the cell temperature in 3 °C, and thus a performance increment has been attained. Moreover, the thermal efficiency can be further improved by a backside thermal insulation, a glazed front side cover and/or a low-emissivity coating on either side of the absorber or inside the glass cover (Proell et al., 2017).

Additionally, PVT technologies can either be coupled with reflectors (to enhance light capture) or be based in flat plate collectors. Solar concentrators focus the incident solar radiation typically into a thermal receiver, which generates thermal energy at higher temperatures and lower heat losses, however, it also includes a drawback by reaching higher stagnation temperatures (Lämmle et al., 2018). Moreover, concentration allows solar collectors to reduce receiver area and cost (Tian et al., 2018), as well as enhancing the annual thermal performance by reducing conduction and convection losses. Stationary low concentration solar collectors typically do not reach temperatures higher than 120 °C, nonetheless, these collectors avoid the need of a tracking system due to reasonably high acceptance angles (Reichl et al., 2013). Several studies focusing on parabolic or compound parabolic troughs have been presented, yielding high thermal and electrical efficiencies as shown by Bellos and Tzivanidis (2019), Valizadeh et al. (2019) and Adam et al.

(2019).

Proell et al. (2016) studied the impact of a Compound Parabolic Collectors (CPC) reflector design on the electrical Incidence Angle Modifier (IAM) profile of crystalline silicon (c-Si) solar cells in a PVT hybrid collector, which concluded that the high incidence angles are the main reason for a non-uniform illumination and therefore a lower electrical power output, due to higher optical losses. The high-intensity solar radiation at normal incidence is a source of complications for many concentrating solar collectors such as material degradation, hot spots and non-uniform illumination, hence a critical topic to address. Hence, and following the detailed work developed by Cabral and Karlsson (2018) on symmetric parabolic solar collectors with central/vertical PVT receivers, a CPVT solar collector composed by a parabolic trough geometry and a wedge PVT receiver has been designed, built and tested. The developed concentrating PVT solar collector presented in this paper aims at shifting the electrical peak power at normal incidence to higher incidence angles and thus, lower the stress and high radiation intensity to which the solar cells are exposed at normal incidence.

To reach the aim of this work, the following paper presents several sets of experimental outdoor tests that have been performed, such as electrical transversal and longitudinal Incidence Angle Modifier charts, daily thermal and electrical performance diagrams (instantaneous measurements), as well as optical and electrical efficiency measurements.

1.1. Concentrating PVT solar collectors

1.1.1. Non-uniform illumination on solar cells

One of the most common issues that decrease the electrical efficiency in PV systems is the non-uniform illumination profile over a series of connected PV cells. Typically, non-uniform illumination profiles are created by positional interferences (such as clouds or buildings), structural (low-quality design) and material imperfections. To understand and avoid positional interferences, shading profile calculations were introduced by Rönnelid and Karlsson (1997), where a solar projection angle θ_p has been defined and schematically shown in the following Fig. 1.

PV modules are normally connected in series, where the electrical

Fig. 1. Solar radiation projection angle θ_p onto a vertical surface with surface normal n .

current generated in each cell is assumed to be identical and proportional to the amount of illumination. The electrical current in a PV cell string will be limited by the cell with the least illumination (Paul et al., 2015) which is often caused by shading from the collector's box frame or due to a short reflector length.

In stationary concentrating solar collectors, shading has to be tackled by typically employing longer reflectors. Transversal shading (defined by the aperture area/acceptance angle) impacts a PV cell string in a more uniform pattern, meaning that the losses are fairly proportional to the shaded area. On the other hand, the longitudinal shading (typically caused by the solar collector box frame) causes the edge cells to have less current than the following ones, thus amplifying greatly the effect of shading (described in Cabral et al., 2019). Moreover, by placing a PV cell under a concentrating system, reflection and mismatching losses occur, which leads to a decrease in electrical efficiency. Moreover, practical reflector surfaces have non-uniformities in the slope which generate optical errors that distort the reflected image.

1.2. LCPVT solar collector

A wedge PVT receiver shape has been designed to accommodate 24 quarter-size monocrystalline PV cells connected in series (hand-soldered), on each receiver side. The receiver has been placed 41 mm above the centre section of the parabolic reflector geometry and makes an angle of 20° between the two receiver copper plates. The solar collector trough is characterized by an aperture of 323 mm and a parabolic reflector depth of 144 mm, as shown in the following Fig. 2.

The tilt angle that each receiver copper plate has (10° from the normal), aims at increasing (on the transversal direction) the amount of radiation received directly onto the PV cells and also to lower the electrical peak power to which the solar cells are exposed at normal incidence. For simplicity, each side of the PVT receiver has been named 'receiver side 1-bottom and 2-top' for south or north orientation, respectively.

Fig. 2. Cross-section (with dimensions in millimetres and degrees) view of the parabolic trough solar collector with a wedge PVT receiver.

Table 1

Summary of the main parameters that characterize the PV cells.

Efficiency [%]	P_{mpp} [W]	V_{mpp} [V]	I_{mpp} [A]	V_{oc} [V]	I_{sc} [A]	Dimension[mm]
20.1	1.1	0.5	2.2	0.6	2.4	78x78

Cabral et al. (2019) showed that the longitudinal incident radiation has the biggest impact in the performance of LCPVT solar collectors, therefore, the design concept collector box has been limited to 170 by 2440 mm. Both receiver copper plates are connected by a 12 mm diameter black copper pipe with a wall thickness of 1 mm, where the HTF flows. The receiver has an outer width of 82 mm (inner width of 80 mm) and a length of 2000 mm, where a silicone gel from Wacker (Elastosil Solar 2205) with a thermal conductivity of $0.2 \text{ W/m}\cdot^\circ\text{C}$ and light transmittance of around 97% has been used to encapsulate the PV cells. Additionally, a reflector plate (Almeco Vega 295SP) with 92% of reflectance has been selected. Moreover, the main characteristics of the PV cells from Big Sun Energy are presented in the following Table 1.

Furthermore, a low iron solar glass (from Scheuten Glas) and a PMMA side gable protection with a thickness of 4 mm has been selected. The main parameters that characterize both side gables and the collector glass cover are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Summary of the main parameters that characterize the low iron solar glass and the PMMA side gables.

	Emissivity [%]	Thickness [mm]	Thermal conductivity [W/ $\text{m}\cdot^\circ\text{C}$]	Transmittance ^a [%]
Cover, Solar glass	84	4	1	91 [+/- 0.5]
Gable, PMMA	94	4	0.2	92 [+/- 1]

^a Reference to ISO 9050. Restricted to wavelengths from 0.3 to 1.2 μm .

Table 3
Summary of the main parameters of the receiver and reflector geometry design concept.

Geometry	Concentration factor (C_i)	Reflector depth [mm]	Receiver dimensions (L/W/T) [mm]	Air gap ^a [mm]	Gap ^b [mm]	Receiver tilt angle [°]	Aperture [mm]
Parabola	2.0	144	2000/82/3.4	22	41	10	323

^a Distance between top receiver side and glass cover, aiming to reduce convection losses (Duffie and Beckman, 2013).

^b Distance between bottom receiver side and reflector plate.

The nominal electrical peak power per square meter of aperture (for a module temperature of 25 °C at normal incidence) is around 80 $W_{p,el}$ for a concentration ratio (C_i) of 2. Furthermore, the CPVT thermal peak power per square meter of aperture (while electricity is generated at $[(\Delta T/2) - T_{amb}]/I_{tot} = 0 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}\cdot\text{m}^2/\text{W}$) is 503 $W_{p,th}$. Each trough is characterized by an effective area of around 0.79 m^2 and the main characteristics of the receiver and reflector geometry are presented in the following Table 3.

2. Experimental test method and equipment description

2.1. Testing equipment description for thermal and electrical measurements

Fig. 3 shows the experimental schematic setup (technical drawing scheme) that has been used for both electrical and thermal measurements which measures inlet, outlet and ambient temperature, pressure, flow rate, and global and diffuse solar radiation. A water-cooled hybrid CPVT solar collector has been evaluated, built and installed in the outdoor testing laboratory at Gävle University (Sweden) with a variable south-oriented collector tilt angle (β) depending on the nature of the tests.

The test setup apparatus consists of a solar collector closed-loop and a domestic hot water open-loop. Furthermore, the solar collector loop relates to the HTF flowing between the collector and heat exchanger, supplied by a fixed flow rate. A mixture of 80% of pure water and 20% of ethylene glycol (with a heat capacity of 2200 J/Kg.K) has been used as HTF (overall heat capacity of 3813 J/Kg.K).

Table 4
Thermal measurement equipment and respective accuracy deviation.

Thermal measurement equipment	Data	Deviation
Flow rate \dot{m} [L/m]	0.5–10	±1.5%
Temperature interval ΔT [°C]	0–90	±0.04%
Pressure interval ΔP [Bar]	Up to 6	±1.5%
Heater [°C]	30–90	±0.04%
Pressure transmitter [Bar]	6	±1%

The test rig apparatus consists of a hydraulic and electric circuit designed for performance characterization (both electrical and thermal) of any kind of domestic solar collectors. For thermal performance characterization, the inlet collector temperature was constant for each measurement period (to access the efficiency), and the outlet collector temperature was measured to characterize the thermal behaviour of the collector (presented in sub-sections 3.3 and 3.4). Table 4 presents the closed-loop measurement accuracy.

The closed-loop is composed of the following components:

- Programmable Logic Controller: All regulation and control are done by an Abelko Webmaster Pro/Ultrabase PLC system, which allows for remote control of the system.
- Automated Flow Control: The flow is controlled through a Proportional Integral Derivative (PID) regulated and a frequency-controlled pump, which allows the user to set the desired flow rate and automatically adjust to any in pressure drop.

Fig. 3. Technical drawing of the hydraulic rig composed by several temperature and pressure sensors, a heat exchanger, a vacuum degasser, expansion vessel, mixing tank (for a more homogeneous temperature), as well as a heater for constant inlet temperature.

- Collector Inlet Temperature Control: Incoming hot water from the solar collectors is first cooled by tap water (through a heat exchanger) to a temperature slightly below the desired collector inlet temperature. The water is stored in a 10L tank for buffering and then heated to the desired temperature with a 4.5 kW heater from Relek Produktion AB.
- Temperature Measurement/Thermal performance characterization: PT100s are used to measure inlet and outlet temperatures of thermal collectors, as well as ambient temperature. The inlet and outlet temperature sensors have been installed against the flow, thus creating turbulence within the pipe and therefore yields more accurate measurements (Kalogirou, 2014).
- Vacuum Degasser: For accurate measurement and results, the circuit must be completely free of air. Therefore, a degasser has been installed as it allows the flow to go through a chamber of lower pressure where air bubbles increase in size and are subsequently removed. Water that is free of air will naturally absorb any incoming air from the circuit and therefore the system eventually will be completely air-free (theoretically), even in places where the flow is too low to physically move trapped air bubbles.
- Insulated stainless steel piping: All piping in the test rig is made out of stainless steel pipes which decreases the pressure drop and reduces significantly the possibility of corrosion (Coker, 2007).

For the electrical performance characterization, an I-V tracer (which applies a variable load) is used to measure and plot the I-V diagrams. Furthermore, on the solar loop system, several measurement equipments have been installed to measure the system operation, such as KippZonen CMP3 and CMP6 pyranometers to measure the diffuse and global radiation, respectively. Both pyranometers are installed in the same plane as the solar collector, which make them moving together with the solar collector. Furthermore, all sensors, such as ambient and HTF temperature sensors, pyranometers and flowmeters, are connected to a data acquisition system that monitors, records and processes the data

Table 5
Electrical measurement equipment and respective accuracy deviation.

Electrical measurement equipment	Data	Deviation
Pyranometer CMP3 [W/m ²]	Up to 2000	±1.5%
Pyranometer CMP6 [W/m ²]	Up to 2000	±1%
I-V Tracer [V] [I]	-	0.1%

through a CR1000 datalogger from Campbell Scientific (with time-step record measurements of 30 sec per measurement). Table 5 presents the electrical measurement equipment accuracy.

2.2. Outdoor testing method

2.2.1. Electrical and thermal performance

For both thermal and electrical performance diagrams, the CPVT system has been east–west oriented, with fixed collector tilt throughout the day, which was adjusted to ensure that the incidence angle was optimal for Gävle (coordinates: 60.67°N, 17.14°E).

2.2.2. Electrical incidence angle Modifier testing method

The effective solar height is shown in Fig. 4 (i.e. the south projection angle θ_{NS}), which typically sets the optimum collector tilt angle facing south in the northern hemisphere or facing north in the southern hemisphere.

For a specific position of the sun (i.e. short time interval Δt), the average beam irradiance G_b can be projected into the north–south vertical plane P_{NS} , as shown in Fig. 4. During the equinoxes, the south projection angle is fairly constant (the sun’s path has a profile movement in an east–west plane) during the day, which will be in the normal plane of a glass cover tilted with an angle equal to the latitude. The south projection angle has a daily minimum at noon during summertime when it overlaps with the conventional solar height. For the optimal collector tilt angle on a south-facing surface, the collectors’ surface must be tilted

Fig. 5. South projected angle θ_{NS} for the 28th of July and 27th of August, Gävle (Sweden, Latitude: 60.7°N).

Fig. 4. The solar position (vector 1) has been divided into an east–west direction (vector 2) and a north–south vertical P_{NS} plane (vector 3). The south projection angle θ_{NS} is the angle between the projection of the ‘sun position vector’ into a north–south vertical plane and the south horizon. Where θ_z is the solar zenith angle, γ_s the solar azimuth angle (based on Rönnelid and Karlsson, 1997).

Fig. 6. Solar collector test apparatus for the transversal electrical IAM testing procedure with both pyranometers for global and diffuse radiation measurements.

with an angle of $(90 - \theta_{NS})^\circ$, therefore, the collectors' surface has been placed with a tilt of $(90 - \theta_{NS})^\circ$ at noon for the selected testing days. The testing procedure has been conducted between 11 am and 1 pm, as the projected solar altitude remains constant (negligible error of around 2°) throughout those hours, as can be seen in Fig. 5.

To perform measurements on electrical $IAM_{Transv.}$ (transversal direction), the collector has been placed as shown in Fig. 6 and tilted in the south-north direction. By employing this testing procedure and assisted by a sundial angular device, the angle between the collector and the sun can be constantly adjusted so that the longitudinal direction angle is 0° , which decreases the need of any correction factors, as the projected solar altitude will have a profile movement in an east–west plane.

For the longitudinal electrical IAM, the previously described $IAM_{Transv.}$ procedure has been replicated, however, the collector has been placed in a vertical position (rotated 90° from the position previously shown in Fig. 6) and then tilted in the south-north direction so that the transversal direction angle is 0° .

2.3. Optical efficiency

Several factors such as geometrical losses, optical properties of the cover glazing (transmittance), reflector material (reflectance) and PV cells (absorptance) limit the optical efficiency and thus the electrical and thermal efficiency of a hybrid system. Therefore, the optical efficiency is a key factor to both electrical and thermal performance characterization of a CPVT system.

2.3.1. Theoretical optical efficiency

Eq. (1) has been formulated by Brogen et al. (2000), which give the thermal optical efficiency of a CPVT with a conventional CPC geometry. The effective solar reflectance ρ of a CPC reflector and transmittance of the glazing τ are used to access the thermal optical efficiency presented in the following Eq. (1).

$$\eta_{opt,th} = \frac{\tau \cdot (A_{cell} + A_{reflector} \cdot \rho) \cdot \frac{G_{beam}}{G_{global}}}{A_{aperture}} \quad (1)$$

where A_{cell} and $A_{reflector}$ denotes the projected areas of the PV cell and the reflector, respectively. Moreover, $A_{aperture}$ is the area of the concentrator aperture.

2.3.2. Optical efficiency from I_{sc} measurements

At a constant temperature, the short-circuit current I_{sc} of a concentrating PV system depends on the irradiance on the solar cells and the efficiency of the solar cells. The irradiance on the solar cells is strongly dependent on the efficiency of the optical system. The optical efficiency η_{opt} can be determined from measurements of I_{sc} according to Eq. (2). $I_{sc, standard module}$ gives the short-circuit current of a module at Standard Test Conditions (STC) G_{STC} and equal to 1000 W/m^2 . G is the measured solar irradiance on the concentrator aperture and the C_i is the geometrical concentration ratio. Furthermore, the diffuse fraction has been corrected with a factor of 0.88.

$$\eta_{opt} = \frac{I_{sc, measured}}{I_{sc, standard module}} \cdot \frac{G_{STC}}{C_i \cdot G} \quad (2)$$

2.3.3. Optical efficiency from thermal measurements

Parameters such as flow rate, temperature (inlet, outlet and ambient) and solar radiation (both global and diffuse) were measured during several summer days with various combinations of irradiation, collector temperatures and collector tilt angles. A collector output power Q (presented in Eq. (3)) has been obtained from the combination of the different parameters described previously (Tzivanidis et al., 2015).

$$Q = \rho \cdot V \cdot c_p \cdot (t_{out} - t_{in}) / A_c \quad (3)$$

A simplified model was then used to describe the collector output

power P , with irradiation, peak collector efficiency η_0 and temperature difference as input. The collector output power P calculation is presented in Eq. (4).

$$P = \eta_0 \cdot G - U_1 \cdot \Delta T \quad (4)$$

where,

$$\Delta T = T_{col.} - T_a \quad (5)$$

$$T_{col.} = \frac{T_{out} + T_{in}}{2} \quad (6)$$

From Eq. (4) is then possible to derive the collector efficiency by employing Eq. (7).

$$\eta = \eta_0 - U_1 \cdot \frac{\Delta T}{G} \quad (7)$$

3. Results

In the following section, the electrical and thermal daily power diagrams for both receiver sides 1-bottom and 2-top (for troughs 1-bottom and 2-top), are presented, for a collector tilt of 42° . Also, the optical efficiency from I_{sc} and thermal measurements are presented, as well as, a detailed comparative analysis of both transversal and longitudinal electrical IAM for both receiver sides is offered.

This paper aims to study the performance behaviour of receiver side 1 (for trough 1-bottom) and 2 (for both trough 1-bottom and 2-top). As the cable from receiver side 1 (trough 2-top) has been detached from the PV cell string while rotating the solar collector stand during measurements, no measurements have been collected for receiver side 1 (trough 2-top). Furthermore, a more detailed assessment of the test results is accessible in Appendix A (Table 7).

3.1. Daily electrical power and temperature diagrams

3.1.1. Testing data, July

Two days, one at the end of July and another in August, have been selected to provide a better understanding of the daily performance of the LCPVT solar collector for the two troughs (1-bottom and 2-top) and receiver sides (1 and 2), as well as, the importance of the collector tilt angle in the overall performance of the CPVT solar collector. Therefore, Fig. 7 presents a profile view of the wedge PVT receiver in regards to the solar radiation incidence angle for a collector tilt of 42° for the 28th July (A) and the 27th August (B) at noon.

As the solar altitude varies throughout the year, it was intended to study the electrical performance of the collector at different solar altitudes and therefore to have a displacement between the theoretical optimum collector tilt angle (i.e. projected solar altitude) and the actual

Fig. 7. Solar radiation incidence angle for a collector tilt of 42° for the 28th July (A) and the 27th August (B) at noon.

Fig. 8. Global and diffuse radiation pattern for a typical clear sky day on the 28th of July. The pyranometers are south oriented and placed in the collector plane of 42°, between 7:40 am and 4:55 pm.

solar collector tilt angle of 42°. Both days registered very similar solar radiation patterns, therefore, only the radiation pattern on the 28th of July is presented. Both global and diffuse solar radiation have been collected between 7:40 am and 4:55 pm and have been presented in the following Fig. 8.

As the flow rate, HTF and ambient temperature influence the thermal and electrical efficiency, it is important to follow and understand their pattern. The flow was set to a mean value of 3.4 L/min (time-step of 10 min) for July and is shown in Fig. 9.

In the morning and afternoon, the ΔT is lower than 1 °C. On the other hand, as the ambient temperature and solar radiation rise, the ΔT also rises to around 2 °C, between 11 am and 3 pm. Furthermore, the inlet and outlet HTF temperature presented in Fig. 9 display a similar pattern from trough 1 to trough 2, which shows a good agreement between both troughs.

Fig. 10 shows the instantaneous electrical power per unit of area registered for receiver side 1 and 2 in a clear sky day on the 28th of July, with a mean flow rate of 3.4 L/min for a collector tilt angle of 42°.

The electrical power pattern presented in Fig. 10 for receiver side 1 (trough 1-bottom) is in agreement with Fig. 5, as the projected solar altitude is higher in the mornings/afternoon and lower at midday, thus a higher output during midday and lower output in the morning/afternoon. The sun will not see the bottom absorber during morning and afternoon due to the specific orientation of receiver side 1-bottom (trough 1-bottom). From the electrical power pattern of receiver side 1-bottom (trough 1-bottom), it is also possible to acknowledge that the collector was not fully south oriented as the peak power-point is not

Fig. 9. Outlet and inlet HTF temperatures (left Y-axis), and ambient temperature (right Y-axis) registered for trough 1 and 2 in a clear sky day on the 28th of July, for a collector tilt of 42° and a mean flow rate of 3.4 L/min (time-step of 10 min).

Fig. 10. Electrical power registered for receiver side 1-bottom and 2 (both troughs 1-bottom and 2-top) in a clear sky day on the 28th of July, for a collector tilt of 42° and a mean flow rate of 3.4 L/min and a temperature of around 54 °C.

located at around 12:23 pm (as in Fig. 8) but 12:08 pm. We can assume that the collector had a minor deviation of around 3° towards the east, as one hour typically compresses 15°. On the other hand, this misalignment can be explained by a possible mismatch between the collector and the pyranometers orientation. The electrical power pattern for receiver side 1-bottom follows the solar radiation pattern, due to the tilted receiver side of 10°, which helps to get a similar pattern as the one presented in Fig. 8, reaching an electrical peak power of around 47 W/m². Due to the misalignment, the electrical power pattern for receiver side 2-top (for trough 1 and 2) will have only one electrical peak power in the afternoon (around 3:22 pm), and not two as expected (morning and afternoon). Additionally, both receiver side 2 (for trough 1 and 2) reached an electrical peak power of around 48 W/m².

3.1.2. Testing data, august

A time interval between 9:24 am and 4:24 pm in a clear sky day on the 27th of August has been selected for a mean flow rate of 2.5 L/min (time-step of 10 min). Fig. 11 presents the ambient, inlet and outlet (HTF) temperature patterns for this day.

The collector ΔT progressively increases from 0.5 °C to a maximum ΔT of 2.2 °C, from 9:24 am until 2:04 pm, where it slightly decreases. Additionally, Fig. 12 shows the electrical power registered for receiver side 1 and 2 (both troughs 1 and 2) for a mean flow rate of 2.5 L/min and a collector tilt angle of 42°.

To maximize the annual electrical yield, it is important to adjust the collector tilt, which for this case should have been 52° (i.e. the optimal collector tilt angle is given by 90° - θ_{NS}, with θ_{NS} = 38° at noon), if the electrical peak power was the goal. However, the goal of this test

Fig. 11. Outlet and inlet temperature (time-step of 10 min, mean values) registered for trough 1 and 2 in a clear sky day on the 27th of August, for a collector tilt of 42° and a mean flow rate of 2.5 L/min.

Fig. 12. Electrical power register registered for receiver side 1-bottom and receiver side 2 (both troughs 1-bottom and 2-top) a clear sky day on the 27th of August (from 10:15 am and 2:53 pm), for a collector tilt of 42° and a mean flow rate of 2.5 L/min.

intended to study the influence of the solar altitude on the electrical peak power.

Fig. 12 shows a higher electrical peak power for receiver side 1-bottom (trough 1-bottom) since the angle between the receiver and the collector normal is of 10°, which allows receiver side 1-bottom to get direct radiation from the sun while having lower reflection losses, thus a peak power of 72 W/m² (35%_{rel} higher than in Fig. 10). Moreover, the lower HTF temperature allows the monocrystalline Si solar cells to have a high efficiency, thus a higher electrical peak power.

Concerning receiver side 2 (both trough 1-bottom and 2-top), it can be seen that the electrical peak power is fairly low and constant up to around 2:45 pm, where it increases to around 35 W/m² (27%_{rel} lower than in Fig. 9). The difference between Figs. 10 and 12 lies on a lower solar altitude for August, which favours receiver side 1-bottom as explained in Fig. 7.

3.2. Electrical peak efficiency

One of the most important parameters in a CPVT solar collector is the real electrical efficiency, therefore, Fig. 13 presents the experimental electrical efficiency (per aperture area) for trough 1.

Fig. 13 shows an electrical peak efficiency (i.e. nominal efficiency) for trough 1 of 8% (R² = 0.996) at 25 °C and 4.8% at 57 °C. This means a

Fig. 13. Experimental electrical efficiency per module temperature for trough 1. The module temperature is taken as the HTF fluid temperature since the cell temperature has not been measured.

decrease of around 1.25%/°C, which is higher than expected as the silicon solar cells have an average temperature coefficient of around 0.4%/°C. The temperature has been monitored at the HTF level. PV cells have a higher temperature than the HTF and this difference is expected to be higher at 25 °C than at 57 °C since more heat is transferred from the PV cell to the HTF at 25 °C. As the temperature measurements were done at the HTF level and since the electrical efficiency is dependent of the cell temperature, it is expected a higher nominal efficiency since the electrical peak efficiency presented previously is for an HTF temperature of 25 °C and not for a PV cell temperature of 25 °C. Moreover, the monocrystalline solar cell temperature and illumination can be non-uniform, especially due to the ‘focal line’ created by the reflector, which enhances this phenomenon. The highest temperature spot (commonly known as ‘hot spot’) on the PV cell will set the voltage and efficiency. Furthermore, a possible misalignment in the receiver placement, the PV cell string being hand-soldered (i.e. lower cell efficiency) and due to a portion of the light being reflected to the receiver backside contributes to a lower efficiency.

Additionally, by having only one receiver side electrically operational (leading to higher temperatures), trough 2-top reached an electrical peak efficiency –4.0%_{rel} lower than trough 1-bottom.

3.3. Optical efficiency from I_{sc} measurements

At high irradiation (noon) on a clear day, it was possible to measure the short circuit current I_{sc} = 2.7 A and solar irradiance G = 916 W/m². As the full-size c-Si cell has been cut into 4 quarters and then series-connected, it is expected to have a lower short circuit current. The manufacturer states that the I_{sc} is of 9.6 A, at standard test condition STC (where G is 1000 W/m² for a temperature of 25 °C and an air mass of 1.5). Moreover, the following Table 6 presents the measured optical efficiency according to Eq. (2) and the theoretical optical efficiency from I_{sc} measurements for different incidence angles according to Eq. (1).

Table 6 Measured optical efficiency per angle of incidence between 11:50 am and 2:30 pm.

Angle of incidence [°]	Theoretical opt. efficiency [%]	Measured opt. efficiency [%]
0 [+/- 1]	72	63
5 [+/- 1]	71	61
10 [+/- 1]	70	60
15 [+/- 1]	69	59
20 [+/- 1]	67	58
25 [+/- 1]	64	56
30 [+/- 1]	61	55
35 [+/- 1]	57	53
40 [+/- 1]	53	51

Fig. 14. Instantaneous thermal efficiency diagram of the CPVT hybrid system from thermal measurements for a collector tilt of 42°. The collector is south oriented and placed in the east–west direction, between 8:24 am and 4:44 pm for an HTF temperature of 56 °C on the 27th of August.

The presented measured optical efficiency (at 0° with a value for 63%) for normal incidence differs around -12 %_{rel} from the theoretical optical efficiency (at normal incidence), which can be explained by losses in the hand soldering of the PV cells as well as optical imperfections in the reflector geometry (i.e. optical losses).

3.4. Optical efficiency from thermal measurements

The optical efficiency from thermal measurements is dependent on the geometry, transmittance of the glazing, the reflectance of the reflector and the absorptance of the PV cells. Fig. 14 shows the measured instantaneous daily thermal efficiency, relative to the global radiation for two similar troughs, for time-steps of 10 min.

The misalignment displayed in Fig. 14 (from trough 1 with $\eta_{max} = 45\%$ and 2 with $\eta_{max} = 48\%$) can be explained since the cable from receiver side 1 (trough 2) was unattached from the PV cell string and no electric power was generated. This will lead to higher thermal efficiencies. The measurements were taken for an HTF overall temperature of 56 °C, which increases the losses. On the other hand, as no electric power is generated the thermal production will be higher.

The effective projected solar height determines the optimum tilt angle of a surface facing south for the given time of the year, which is illustrated in Fig. 5. The effective solar height for the 27th of August is fairly constant between 11:44 am and 1:44 pm, which explains the fairly constant thermal efficiency around noon, in Fig. 14.

Additionally, from the instantaneous thermal efficiency diagrams with a fairly constant irradiation pattern (between 850 and 982 W/m²), it is possible to attain the thermal optical efficiency diagram from experimental data, which is presented in the following Fig. 15, for both troughs 1 and 2.

From the slope of the linear regression diagram shown in Fig. 15, it is possible to extract the first-order heat loss coefficient U_1 (W/m².°C), which reached values of 4.1 and 4.0 W/m².°C ($R^2 = 0.996$) for both trough 1-bottom and 2-top, respectively. Moreover, a thermal optical efficiency of 58.3% has been achieved for trough 1-bottom, which leads to a thermal peak efficiency of around 50.3% if electricity is being produced. Additionally, a thermal optical efficiency of 59.9% (i.e. thermal peak efficiency of 52.2% if electricity is generated) is achieved for trough 2-top. As previously stated, only receiver side 2 is electrically

Fig. 15. Experimental efficiency for trough 1-bottom (solid blue line) and 2-top (dashed orange line). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

operational, therefore it is comprehensible that trough 2-top achieved a slightly higher optical efficiency of around + 2.7 %_{rel} than trough 1.

3.5. Electrical longitudinal and transversal incidence angle Modifier

This section presents an analysis of the results obtained for the longitudinal and transversal electrical IAM, where the testing procedure has been described in sub-section 2.2.2. The electrical IAM has been obtained from the incidence angle, global irradiation (W/m²) during clear weather and electrical power per unit of area (W/m²). Fig. 16 presents the normalized experimental electrical IAM for the longitudinal direction.

Furthermore, Fig. 17 presents the normalized experimental electrical transversal IAM diagram for both receiver side 1-bottom and 2-top (trough 1-bottom). It has a maximum deviation of 9.2% between both receiver sides and it can be explained due to a possible misalignment of the PVT receiver, which automatically leads to a minor deviation.

As expected, the transversal IAM is more sensitive than the

Fig. 16. Normalized experimental electrical IAM (combined receiver side 1-bottom and 2-top, from trough 1-bottom), longitudinal direction.

Fig. 17. Normalized experimental electrical IAM (receiver side 1-bottom, 2-top and the combined trough 1-bottom) in the transversal direction.

longitudinal IAM, which can be explained due to the narrow acceptance angle of around 10° (outside of which the drop in efficiency is more pronounced). Additionally, Fig. 17 also shows that the electrical peak efficiency is not reached at normal incidence (typically at 0°), as in a standard flat PVT module, but between 5 and 10° due to the tilt angle between the two receiver sides. This shows that around 8% is lost at normal incidence due to the large angle of incidence at the absorber. Furthermore, the findings presented in this section are in line with the study presented by Koronaki and Nitsas (2018) which states that low-concentrator solar collectors are highly sensitive to high incident angles.

Table 7

Summary of the outdoor testing results on the CPVT, including the first order heat loss coefficient U_1 , measured and theoretical optical efficiency, HTF inlet and outlet temperature ranges, and experimental electrical and thermal efficiencies.

Parameters	U_1 [W/m ² .°C]	Experimental thermal optical efficiency [%] ^a	Experimental thermal peak efficiency [%] ^b	Theoretical optical efficiency [%]	Experimental electrical peak efficiency [%]	Daily electrical peak power [W/m ²]
Receiver side 1 (trough 1)	4.1	58.3	50.3	72	8.0	72
Receiver side 2 (trough 1)						48
Receiver side 2 (trough 2)	4.0	59.9	52.2		7.7	48

^a If electricity is generated.

^b If electricity is not generated.

4. Conclusion

The measurement results made on a low concentration PVT solar collector can be found as follow:

- An overall electrical peak efficiency of 8% has been achieved.
- The thermal optical efficiency reached 58.3% and 59.9% for trough 1 and 2, respectively.
- First-order heat loss coefficients of 4.1 and 4.0 W/m².°C were attained for trough 1 and 2, respectively.
- The electrical transversal IAM for each receiver side reached the electrical peak efficiency at 10° .
- The half-acceptance angle is around 10° .
- The design concept has been successful in reducing the electrical peak power at normal incidence and thus, lower the stress and high radiation intensity to which the solar cells are exposed at normal incidence.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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The output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the

information contained therein.

Appendix A

Table 7 gives a summary of the main outdoor testing results on the CPVT, including the first order heat loss coefficient U_1 , measured and theoretical optical efficiency, daily electrical peak power, and experimental electrical and thermal peak efficiencies described and discussed in section 2 and 3, respectively.

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